

IMPACT OF 1.5% MONOSODIUM GLUTAMATE SOLUTION ON LIPID BIOMARKERS OF ALBINO RATS (*RATTUS NOVERGICUS*)

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Abstract

Monosodium glutamate (MSG) is a common food additive used to enhance flavor in processed foods. Despite being classified as generally safe by regulatory agencies, its potential health effects have been a subject of ongoing research. The trial was done to investigate the effect of MSG on cholesterol level, Triglyceride (TG) level, low density lipoprotein (LDL), and High-density lipoprotein (HDL) level of albino rats. The findings of the current study demonstrate that the effect of MSG on lipid profile (including Free Cholesterol, triglyceride, LDL, and HDL-C) leads to a significant increase in mild doses compared to the control group. It was observed that there was a notable increase in cholesterol levels, triglycerides, and low-density lipoprotein (LDL), accompanied by a decrease in high-density lipoprotein (HDL). The average triglyceride values in the control group of male rats were 122.7320, whereas in the MSG group, it was 122.0340, resulting in a difference of 0.69800. Similarly, the average cholesterol values in the control group were 153.9920, whereas in the MSG group, it was 110.9880, resulting in a group.

INTRODUCTION

Concerns related to the use of MSG in food to cause obesity in humans were raised by data from animal research in which neonatal injection of MSG provided a model of obesity with impaired glucose tolerance and insulin resistance. The mechanisms of MSG's influence on metabolism have been the subject of more theories. The effects of MSG on energy balance include making food more palatable and interfering with the

hypothalamus signalling cascade that controls leptin function (He *et al.*, 2011). (Hermanussen and Tresguerres 2003) The inflammatory basis of MSG-induced obesity was revealed in 19-week-old rats that received 2 mg/g and 4 mg/g of MSG subcutaneous injections on postnatal days 2 and 4, respectively, and 6 mg/g and 8 mg/g injections on postnatal days 6, 8 and 10. MSG increased insulin, resisting, and leptin levels in the blood as well as the

mRNA expression of interleukin-6, tumor necrosis factor-alpha, resisting, and leptin in visceral adipose tissue. It also decreased glucose tolerance (Roman-Ramos *et al.*, 2011).

MSG has been used to make adult laboratory mice obese in the past. This is due to the damage it causes in the hypothalamus' arcuate nucleus, which causes a rise in caloric intake exceeding calorie utilization (Ganong *et al.*, 2005). MSG has been demonstrated to cause epileptic seizures in rats. With age, both the frequency and severity of deaths gradually rose. In adult male Wistar rats, MSG has a harmful effect on the test is because it significantly increases aberrant sperm morphology and oligozoospermia in a dose-dependent manner (Onakewhor *et al.*, 2017). The sodium salt of the amino acid L-glutamic acid is monosodium glutamate (MSG), also referred to as sodium glutamate. Its IUPAC name is sodium 2-aminopentanedioate, and the carboxyl group's sodium atom stands in for the hydrogen atom. When German chemist Karl Heinrich Ritthausen experimented with wheat gluten and sulfuric acid to discover and identify L-glutamic acid (the natural form of glutamate) in 1866, the word "glutamate" was born. Japanese chemist Kikunae Ikeda discovered the most notable feature of glutamic acid and its salts up until 1908. It all began with a taste assessment of the predominant flavor of dashi (Thuy *et al.*, 2020).

Following injection or oral administration of MSG, studies in suckling rodent pups revealed serious physiological abnormalities and substantial obesity. Some of these animal models displayed fasting hyperinsulinemia, hyperleptinemia, adiposity, and a rise in plasma fatty acids and triacylglycerols (Seiva *et al.*, 2012). When MSG is given to newborn rats, the neurons in the hypothalamic arcuate nucleus develop different abnormalities. The loss of neurons affects pituitary and adrenal activity, insulin and leptin signalling, and energy homeostasis (Yin *et al.*, 2013). These effects are primarily related to the young animals' immature blood-brain barriers (Boonnate *et al.*, 2015). The excitatory neurotransmitter glutamate has a significant role in both physiological and pathological processes in the mammalian central nervous system (CNS) (Mattson *et al.*, 2008). There are six different types of

glutamate receptors, including three families of ionotropic receptors (NMDA, AMPA, and kainate), and three families of metabotropic receptors (mGluR) (Meldrum *et al.*, 2000). They control numerous essential metabolic and autonomic functions in the central nervous system, which includes the amygdala, hippocampus, and hypothalamus (Collison *et al.*, 2012).

Because liver transaminases were drastically suppressed, researchers surmised that MSG might cause liver damage as a result of nonalcoholic steatohepatitis, which would then increase inflammation. (Roman-Ramos *et al.*, 2011) It has also been demonstrated in 32-week-old C57BL/6J mice whose mothers were fed low-dose dietary monosodium glutamate (0.64 g/l; 97 mg/kg) throughout gestation and were weaned onto the same diet that liver changes are associated with adipose tissue metabolism in nonalcoholic steatohepatitis. MSG raised the expression of numerous adipocyte differentiation-related genes and increased the production of insulin, bile, free fatty acids, and triglycerides in the blood (Collison *et al.*, 2010b). Further investigation into the potential protective benefits of many compounds, particularly antioxidants, was sparked by studies that provided evidence of the harmful consequences of MSG ingestion. Male albino rats' cerebellar cortex was exposed to toxic nerve cell and astrocyte glial fibrillary acidic protein damage for 14 days while receiving vitamin C at a dose of 100 mg/kg/day via a metal orogastric tube along with MSG at a dose of 3 g/kg/day mixed with food (Hashem *et al.*, 2012). The effects of MSG on the superoxide dismutase and catalase activity in the liver, kidney, and brain of MSG-treated rats (4 mg/g, intraperitoneally for 10 days) were effectively mitigated by all vitamins C (200 mg/kg), vitamin E (200 mg/kg), and quercetin (10 mg/kg) when administered orally. These vitamins also modulated glutathione levels and glutathione-S-transferase activity. In serum alanine aminotransferase, aspartate aminotransferase, and -glutamyl transferase, all antioxidants decreased the MSG-increase (Farombi and Onyema 2006).

MSG consumption and its harmful consequences have also been linked to a number of other systems. The subject of MSG as an asthma trigger has

received the greatest attention. Despite a few anecdotal reports linking MSG sensitivity to asthma, reviews have revealed that these studies lacked a reliable experimental design and could not be replicated in order to provide proof that MSG is connected to an asthma response. (Freeman 2006, Beausoleil *et al.*, 2007). Additionally, a more recent investigation on dietary habits and MSG use in Chinese individuals was unable to establish a link between MSG and asthma (Shi *et al.*, 2012b). Additionally, there is little proof to back up adults with chronic asthma avoiding MSG (Zhou *et al.* 2012), which is supported by an animal study using a mouse model of ovalbumin-induced asthma that was fed a diet containing 0.5% or 5% MSG for the week leading up to the first ovalbumin injection and for the following three weeks. MSG had no effect on eosinophil infiltration, production of Th2 cytokines, circulating Age concentrations in the lungs, or the induced airway hyperresponsiveness (Yoneda *et al.*, 2011).

There is evidence from numerous researches that MSG-induced obesity is related to other systems. Compared to control rats, MSG-injected obese rats had higher mean arterial blood pressure and less variability in their heart rates, bradycardia, and responses to vigil and sympathetic stimulation at 33 weeks of age (Konrad *et al.*, 2012). While control animals mobilised brown adipose tissue lipids following exposure to 4 degrees Celsius for six hours, obese mice caused by MSG showed a much higher decline in core temperature after acute cold exposure (4 degrees C for two hours). The authors suggested that the decreased activation of thermogenic pathways in brown adipose tissue in MSG-treated mice led to faulty cold-induced thermogenesis (Moss *et al.*, 1985). Monosodium glutamate (MSG) is a common food additive used to enhance flavor in processed foods. Despite being classified as generally safe by regulatory agencies, its potential health conditions effects have been a subject of ongoing research. The impact of MSG on lipid metabolism has been of particular interest, given the association between abnormal lipid profiles and various health conditions. To investigate this further, a study was conducted on 20 wistar rats to assess the effect of MSG on their lipid profile. The results of this study provided

insights into the potential impact of MSG consumption on human lipid metabolism and contribute to the development of better-informed public health policies.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Experimental site:

The trial was conducted in animal house in the Department of Zoology, Islamia University of Bahawalpur, Pakistan. Bahawalpur lies 112 meter above sea level. The climate is hot and dry. The mean annual temperature is 28.33degree centigrade, the month of June being hottest when daily maximum temperature increases.

Chemicals:

Monosodium glutamate

L-glutamic acid, a flavoring agent that naturally occurs in many foods, is the source of monosodium glutamate (MSG). L-glutamic acid is a non-essential amino acid, which means that it may be produced by your body on its own and is not dependent on food sources. MSG is a crystalline powder that is white, flavourless, and frequently used as a food additive. It is referred to as E621 in the food business. With little effort, it dissolves in water and separates into sodium and free glutamate. It affects an animal's liver, kidney, lipid profile, and hematology.

Test Organisms

10 wistar albino rats were purchased from CIDS (cholistan institute of desert) .All of these rats having different ages, different weight but same gender i.e. males. All of these rats were kept in a small wooden box according to their groups. Rats were given with basic rat diet in the form of pallets two times in a day. Water was given as tap water to group C(control group) and in the form of stock solution of MSG and ditilled water. Suitable room temperature and light was provided to rats.

Experimental Design:

The rats kept in the large wood box having many parts. Wooden box having wooden floor, three walls of iron mesh, having height 3.5 ft, having length of 2ft, it was placed inside the room. The rat room temperature was maintained 24 to 29 degree

centigrade with 40 to 45 percent humidity conditions and it was provided by normal photoperiod all over the day. All the rats were divided into two groups and the groups were B and C. Group B and C having 5 rats in each where C group was considered as control group having 5 rats. Group B exposed to certain concentration of monosodium glutamate respectively. Control group was provided with tap water. All of these rats kept under hygienic conditions and in the same environment. Salt i.e. MSG was given in water to rats by making certain solution.

Dose preparation:

Stock solution of 1.5% sodium chloride was prepared by dissolving 15g of sodium chloride in distilled water to make a final volume of 1000 ml solution. Then this stock solution was administrated daily at ad-labium in the form of water feeder bottles with open access to each animal. This solution was freshly prepared and replaced daily.

RESULTS

Table No. 4.1. Effects of 1.5% Monosodium glutamate solution on the lipid profile of male albino rats (*Rattus norvegicus*)

Lipid biomarkers	Mean±SEM		F-value	P-value	Significance
	CG	EG			
Triglyceroide	122.7±12.5	122±13.1	0.0	0.999	SNS
LDL	85.8±8.87	89±7.86	0.048	0.833	SNS
Cholestrol	153.9±23.7	110.9±14.6	3.098	0.116	SNS
HDL	45.4±8.83	49.0±7.26	0.536	0.485	SNS

CG=Control group, EG=Experimental group, SEM=Standard error mean, SNS=statistically not significant

Sample test was useful to estimate the effect of 1.5% monosodium glutamate solution in albino rats as compared to control group. It is observed that the concentration of Triglycerides in experimental group (122±13.1) is same as control group(122.7±12.5). It is detected that the concentration of cholesterol is non-significantly decreased in experimental group(110.9±14.6) provided with 1.5% MSG solution as compared to control group(153.9±23.7) provided with tap water.

Sample/Blood Collection:

Albino rats were anesthetized with chloroform and blood was collected for the purpose of serum separation. Blood was collected in test tubes having clot activator and then blood was collected in separate Eppendorf. Blood was divided into two parts. One for the study of hematological parameters and second for serum biochemical profiling. Serum samples were frozen and stored at -20°C until used for biochemical analysis. Firstly, blood was collected in serum separator tube. Then it was centrifuge by using centrifugation machine at 2000rpm for 15 min.

Statistical Analysis:

After calculating, concentration of all parameters of lipid profile, data was organized using Microsoft Excel 2007 and for the comparison of mean values of control group and treatment group. Student t-test was applied using IBM SPSS statistics 2020 version 27.0.1.0

It is considered that concentration of LDL is non-significantly increased in experimental group (89±7.86) as compared to control group(85.8±8.87). It is detected that the concentration of HDL is non-significantly increased in experimental group(49.0±7.26) as compared to control group (45.4±8.83). The test was useful to estimate the effects of 1.5% MSG in experimental group as compared to control group.

Discussion

Cholesterol is a waxy substance found in blood of all animals. Body of organisms needs cholesterol to

build healthy cells, but high levels of cholesterol can increase your risk of heart disease. 1.5% monosodium glutamate may increase the cholesterol level in rat. Our analysis showed that 1.5% monosodium glutamate resulted in decrease in cholesterol about 43 mg/dL (153.9±23.7 to 110.9±14.6) in 15days. These represents non-significant effect (p=0.116). These results agree with (Olaleye *al.*, 2014). There results show significant change in cholesterol level. The Mean±SEM values of cholesterol level changed form 1.37±1.00 to 2.39 ± 0.21 mmol/l.

Triglycerides are a type lipid that circulates in blood of organisms. They are the most common type of fat. Our study shows that 1.5% monosodium glutamate solution show no change in triglycerides in 15 days. These represents non-significant effect (p=0.9). These results disagree with (Olaleye *et al.*, 2014). There results show significant change in triglycerides level. The Mean±SEM values of triglycerides level changed form 0.33 ± 0.03 to 1.51±0.22 mmol/l.

LDL (low-density lipoprotein) cholesterol, sometimes called “bad” cholesterol, makes up most of body’s cholesterol. High levels of LDL cholesterol raise your risk for heart disease and stroke. 1.5% monosodium glutamate solution may increase LDL level. Our results show that 1.5% monosodium glutamate solution results in increase of 4 mg/dL(85.5±8.87 to 89±7.86) LDL cholesterol in 15 days. These results agree with (Olaleye *at al.*, 2014). There results show significant change in LDL cholesterol level. The Mean±SEM values of LDL cholesterol level changed form 0.18 ± 0.05 to 0.9 ± 0.04 mmol/l.

HDL (high-density lipoprotein) cholesterol, sometimes called “good” cholesterol, absorbs cholesterol in the blood and carries it back to the liver. The liver then flushes it from the body. Our results show that 1.5% monosodium glutamate solution results in increase of 4mg/dL(45.4±8.83 to 49±7.26) HDL cholesterol in 15 days. These results agree with (Olaleye *et al.*, 2014). There results show slight change in HDL cholesterol level. The Mean±SEM values of HDL cholesterol level changed form 0.80 ± 0.04 to 0.35 ± 0.13 mmol/l.

ADD MORE DATA.....

CONCLUSION

The present study concluded that MSG effect on lipid profile (Free Cholesterol, triglyceride, LDL and HDL-C) is significance increase in mild dose compared with control. There is observed significant increase in cholesterol level, triglycerides, and low density lipoprotein but decrease in high density lipoprotein. The mean values of triglycerides control group and MSG group of male rats 122.7320 and 122.0340 respectively and there difference is 0.69800. The mean values of cholesterol control group and MSG group of male rats 153.9920 and 110.9880 respectively and there difference is 43.00400 .The mean values of LDL control group and MSG group of male rats 85.8000 and 89.0000 respectively and there difference -3.20000. The mean values of LDL control group and MSG group of male rats 45.4800 and 49.0100 respectively and there difference is -3.53000 MSG increases cholesterol, TG, and LDL level in the body while decrease HDL level.

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